

Detection and Determination of Cerium with *p*-Aminophenylmercaptoacetic Acid

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CERIUM is the only lanthanide that can be determined selectively in the presence of other rare earths by oxidation of Ce^{III} to Ce^{IV} , which is a very versatile oxidising agent¹. Cerium(IV) reacts with many organic compounds to give coloured products. Hearn and Kinghorn² used cerium(IV) solution as a reagent for the detection of aromatic amines. Among the few reagents proposed for the detection of cerium(IV) may be mentioned *p*-aminoacetophenone³, sulphanic acid⁴, *p*-anisidine⁵ and benzidine⁶. In these methods, the coloured products formed are not sufficiently stable and also, some are subject to many interferences.

p-Aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid has been used as a reagent for the detection of manganese(II)⁷ and determination of palladium(II)⁸, iron(III)⁹ and used as a diazotisable¹⁰⁻¹³ amine for spectrophotometric determination of nitrite. We have observed that cerium(IV) gives violet colour with *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid. A direct and simple method is now proposed for the detection and determination of cerium(IV) with *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid as a reagent.

Experimental

Spectral measurements were made with a Varian 634-S spectrophotometer. *p*-Aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid (98.1% purity; Evans Chemetics) was used as such. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. A stock solution of cerium(IV) was prepared by dissolving ammonium cerium(IV) sulphate in dilute (1–2 M) H_2SO_4 and standardised volumetrically¹. *p*-Aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid solution (0.2%) was prepared in 0.45 M HCl or 0.22 M H_2SO_4 . Buffer solution (pH~4) was prepared by dissolving sodium acetate (86 g) in distilled water (1 dm³) and adding glacial acetic acid (390 ml). Poly(vinyl alcohol) solution (1%) was prepared from commercially available PVA in warm distilled water. Various solutions of diverse ions used for the interference studies were prepared in distilled water to give 10 mg ml⁻¹ of the respective interfering ions.

Procedures: To a mixture of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (0.01 ml) and polyvinylalcohol (0.01 ml), placed on a spot-plate, were added *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid (0.01 ml) and the test solution (0.01 ml) and mixed. An immediate

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violet colour stable for 30 min appeared, indicating the presence of cerium(IV). The limit of detection is 0.3 μg Ce in the 0.01 ml of test solution.

For the estimation of Ce^{IV} , an aliquot of sample solution containing 50–2000 μg Ce^{IV} was mixed with sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer solution (5 ml), polyvinylalcohol solution (1 ml) and 0.2% *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid (1 ml). The solution was shaken well and diluted to 25 ml with distilled water, when a violet colour developed immediately remaining stable for 30 min. The absorbance was measured at 545 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of the product obtained by oxidation of *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid with cerium(IV) in the pH range 4–5 has a broad maximum at 545 nm ($\epsilon=1950$ units); absorbance value of the reagent blank was less than 0.002 under similar condition. Satisfactory results were obtained with 1 ml of 0.2% *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid in 0.45 *M* HCl or 0.22 *M* H_2SO_4 . The coloured product formed was found to be unstable and its absorbance value changed rapidly. A sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer solution (5 ml; pH \sim 4) was used to maintain the final acidity. Colour of the product was found to be stable for 10 min only. Polyvinylalcohol has been used as a colour stabilising agent¹⁴. A 1 ml solution of PVA was tried as a colour stabilising agent. The coloured product was found to be stable for 30 min. The PVA solution could be varied from 1 to 5 ml of 1% solution without effect. The colour development was found to be independent of temperature in the range 15–50°.

Beer's law is valid from 2.0 to 80 ppm of cerium(IV). The Sandell's sensitivity was found to be 0.072 μg cm^{-2} . Under the optimised conditions, the reproducibility of the method was checked on nine replicate determinations of cerium(IV) over a period of nine consecutive days. The relative standard deviations were found to be 1.70, 1.49 and 1.06% at the respective concentrations of 8, 20 and 40 ppm of cerium(IV).

The effect of interferents that generally accompany cerium has been studied at a cerium concentration of 8 ppm. The tolerance limits (ppm) of foreign ions and compounds are as follows: Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mo^{VI} , Mn^{II} , Al^{III} , Cr^{III} , Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} (100); Y^{III} , Zr^{IV} , La^{III} and Th^{IV} (600); Zn^{II} , Bi^{III} , Pb^{II} and UO_2^{II} (400), phosphate (100), dichromate, Fe^{III} , V^{V} , Ti^{IV} (20), Sr^{II} (2000). Rare earths, iodate, bromate, sulphate, oxalate, nitrate, citrate and EDTA do not interfere. Fluoride interferes seriously.

Cerium was determined in monazite samples by the proposed method. Monazite ore was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid¹⁵. Ce^{III} was oxidised to Ce^{IV} either with potassium bromate¹⁶ or persulphate¹⁷ using Ag^{I} as catalyst. Distilled

water was added to a final acidity of 0.22 *M* H_2SO_4 and cerium was estimated according to the proposed procedure. The results obtained are as given, Ce, 21.97 and 21.65% (proposed method), 21.44 and 20.86% (sulphanilic acid method) respectively, which are in reasonable agreement with those obtained by radiochemical neutron activation method¹⁸.

Rapid colour development, simplicity, temperature independence and colour stability are the advantages of the proposed method. The selectivity of the proposed procedure allows the routine determination of cerium in monazite samples over a wide range of concentrations.

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